

INTERNATIONAL BORDERS AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

International border shave become a complex issue in the global system with economic, social, and security implications, capable of diminishing a nation's effort towards development. The main reason given for these concerns is the porosity of the borders. Previous research has primarily focused on the arbitrary nature of African borders and thus has been unable to extricate gaps between border porosity from emerging trends in border management- a potentially vital instrument considering the intensification of border-related matters globally. Borders and sustainable development are interdependent. The study adopts the survey research design; 250 questionnaires were administered to respondents in border communities' of Katsina and Zamfara States, where Nigeria shares a border with the Republic of Niger and Chad. Espousing the securitisation and political realism theory, it examined how challenges emanating from Nigeria's international borders have impacted the achievement of Goal 1 (Poverty) and Goal 4 (Quality Education) of the sustainable development goals. Contrary to what has been often assumed, border porosity is a consequence and not a cause of border security in Nigeria, as it is the nature of borders to be porous. The findings revealed that the government's neglect of securing its borders through a comprehensive strategy, upgrading its border management practices, and equipping its border posts has undermined sustainable development in border communities in Nigeria. The study recommends that Nigeria's border management system be redesigned to meet global standards.

Keywords: International border, border security, sustainable development, security challenges, poverty.

Introduction

International border (IB) activities have become indispensable globally; the power to secure its national borders is one of the standards used to categorise states as robust, weak and failed in the international system (Osimen, Anegbode, Akande & Oyewole ,2017)). In international relations, borders are perceived as a domain that is linked to the pursuit of national interests, that is, where countries have interests that they seek to maximise in an anarchical global system (Isnblog,2015). International border issues generally cut across legal and security issues but with dire economic consequences as security is a prerequisite for development, thereby making incidents such as international conflict and crime across borders a significant issue in the international arena (Salmon & Imber, 2008), and a priority in risk management. International borders (IBs) are the delineation between one nation and another in the international system, the dividing lines between countries or nations. For this reason, it has been rightly observed that "no borders, no nations" (Agnew, 2007). On the other hand, sustainable development is a coordinated transition involving an increase in resources, a purposeful investment, and an update of technological processes among different institutions,

increasing the potential for achieving human needs (Vare & Scott, 2007). Activities that take place at IBs can lead to development in the short and long run, and if well managed can be sustainable. This is because IBs serve as a transit route that brings in both opportunities and threats that may lead to poverty reduction and reduced hunger which are vital elements for economic development.

Sustainable development entails the creation of continual improvements in the quality of life for all people (Ejumudo, 2015). The United Nations' sustainable development goals (SDGs) are targeted at ensuring a more equitable world; this paper addresses Goal 1-Poverty and Goal 4-Quality Education. This stems from the fact that both goals have not only been severely affected by the challenges emanating from Nigeria's international borders, but have had a multiplier effect on the attainment of other goals. The border communities; Jibia and Kankara local government areas in Katsina State and Zurmi local government area in Zamfara State were selected because the communities share border with the Republic of Niger and Chad, which are hot spots of insurgency, banditry, cattle rustling and kidnapping which have affected farming activities, interrupted school calendar and led to the closure of schools and businesses in the study area

Sankore (2018) posits that demography is destiny and affirms that there is a nexus between literacy rate, poverty and banditry in Zamfara State, where about 80% of people have no secondary education, and foresees an exponential increase in insurgency due to these factors. Poverty and education, which are the focus of this study, have been fingered as twin factors that militate against sustainable development. Ladan, (2019) and Habibu, (2020) assert that abject poverty has created mercenaries who work as informants or logistic suppliers to the bandits operating from the Rugu Forest, which spans over 220km from the Niger Republic to Katsina and Zamfara states. Data on the literacy index issued by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) shows that Katsina State is among the States in Nigeria where the majority of the people can neither read nor write (Amzat, 2017). Similarly, according to the UNESCO (2023) literacy rate ranking for states in Nigeria; Zamfara has a 33.9% and Katsina State 21.7% literacy rate respectively, which they aver is too low and is capable of submerging national and global effort of an improved economy, better health and sustainable development (Punch, 2023).

According to the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (2022), the novel economic, health and security crisis confronting developing countries such as Nigeria can obstruct efforts at sustainable development and swallow the little progress already made. Ladan (2019); Suliema (2021); Mailabari and Hamidu (2015) have identified some of the challenges to sustainable development in Nigeria: insurgency, terrorism, banditry, kidnapping, smuggling, drug and human trafficking, small arms and light weapons proliferation ethnic and religious crisis, corruption, weak institutions and poverty. Lately, the challenge of international borders has been added as detrimental to sustainable development efforts in Nigeria. According to Ikome (2012), while well-defined borders act as a catalyst for building economically stable states, porous borders have been seen as recipes for instability and conflict.

Despite the efforts of the Nigerian Customs and Immigration Service, which are the two agencies charged with international border security, the challenges of international borders

persist. There is a general perception that the Nigerian government needs help with the problem of providing adequate border security, and the ineffectual management of Nigeria's national border has been a serious concern to deal with (Nosiri & Ohazurike, 2016). This has led to loss of revenue for the government and furthered internal unrest in the country. The subject of international borders has become imperative more than ever before; this explains why more developed countries like the United States of America and Israel have always prioritised their borders and addressed it from the perspective of national interest, for whatever challenges a nation's territorial integrity is a direct challenge on the sovereignty of the nation as a whole.

International border challenges cannot be separated from the security issue. Globally, the government's primary responsibility is the provision of security for its citizens. However, by failing to secure their international borders, governments become the major potential threat through these borders to people within their countries (Jackson & Sorensen, 2018), especially in developing countries where international borders have become ungoverned spaces occupied by criminals. Nigeria and other African borders have a poor reputation and are considered as porous (Nosiri & Ohazurike, 2016). Arguably, the insecurity posed by the neglect of the international borders compromises existing fragile national development and erodes all efforts at attaining sustainable development. This may have informed the decision of the United Nations (UN) to prioritise international borders as a security issue and provide a certified code of conduct and non-bidding policies on Border Security Management (BSM) and Border Security Initiative (BSI).

Philip and Osimen (2022), in a qualitative study on Border Security Management and ECOWAS Protocol on Free Movement in West Africa, observed that the poor implementation of the ECOWAS protocol on free movement in the West African sub-region has furthered international border security challenges. The study identified that corruption, inadequate high-tech devices, and porosity are significant impediments to effective border management in the region. However, though the aforementioned challenges were identified, the study failed to establish their extent. The study recommends an increased budget for border management, using modern technological equipment, proper training of security personnel, and a collaborative Joint Task Force in the region.

Adeyemi and Makanjuola (2020), in a content descriptive analysis study of the borderline in Nigeria's northeast and the activities of the multi-national joint task force, observed that African leaders are indifferent about redefining inherited colonial borders. Evidence from the study established a nexus between insurgency and the undefined nature of the international borders with Niger, Chad and Cameroon, mainly due to the overlapping pattern in community settlement, which favours trafficking and serves as a shelter for insurgents. It concludes that with the nature of shared border lands between northern Nigeria and its neighbours, the fight against insecurity remains a hurdle. The study, however, needed to establish the extent of this relationship and its impact on insurgency. The study recommends a better policy for creating a safe environment in the region.

Ladan (2019), in an analysis of contemporary issues in Katsina, adopts a focus group discussion methodology in Jibia, Batsari, Safana and Kankara LGAs, which share a border with Niger Republic and a boundary with Zamfara State to the west. The study found that the

large forest reserves neglected by the government, high levels of poverty and illiteracy, and limited security personnel, among other factors, continue to foster insecurity and hamper government efforts at development. Ladan's (2019) recommendations were generic and not specific, admonishing that the government should strategise on a new course of action to tackle the menace.

Nosiri and Ohazurike (2016) examined the impact of border security on national security in Nigeria using secondary data sources. They used descriptive methodology to analyse the data; it was determined that border security had become a menace in Nigeria, furthering the incursion of insurgency and terrorism and causing loss of government revenue via smuggling and human trafficking. These factors are buttressed by corruption, inadequate border management instruments, and the porosity of Nigeria's border.

The African Economic Development Institute (2015), in an empirical study on the impact of border security on economic development in Africa, opined that the Nigerian state loses approximately 64% of its GDP to informal trade across African borders. The study recommends a cross-regional approach to addressing security issues. However, the study overlooks the impact of these security issues on the persons or community occupying the borders.

Willie and Okunade (2021) examined the nexus between border management and Nigeria's national security, applying a documentary research design using a case study approach with a mixture of primary and secondary data backed by reports from the International Organisation of Migration and the International Crisis Group. The result links the growing security issues in Nigeria to the permeability and inadequate management of Nigeria's borders. He recommends that the Nigerian government must depart from the traditional form of security to the non-traditional form of security aligned to the peculiarity of the 21st century. Ahmed and Abanimebon (2022) examined the patterns, implications and management of migration, border control and issues in Nigeria. Using secondary research methodology, it observed that the inefficiency of state institutions and agencies is responsible for the challenges emanating from Nigeria's international borders. The study recommends that good governance via human security submission, fair distribution of income and social security, rather than law enforcement, would help tackle the challenges of Nigeria's international border.

Statement of the Problem

International borders are situated within the convergence of cultural heritage, a community, and the country; some vital components that make up a border include the people, their culture, government policies, and market forces (Riggs, 2017; Brunet-Jailly & Dupeyron, 2007). Whether borders are artificial, cultural or natural, the government has an obligation to the operational nature of the borders, making them a consequence of dynamic concessions. Thus, it is apparent that there is nothing like a perfect border (Sorel, 2017; Guo, 2015). Therefore, government policies, to a large extent, shape the structures of their international border. For example, while the Canadian government has taken an economic position towards border issues for the United States of America, security shapes all border issues (Hataley, 2006). Existing studies (Osimen, 2017; Olukayode, O. E. & Urhie, E. (2014) established the nexus between international border challenges and sustainable development. According to these

studies, the artificial and arbitrary nature of international borders, porosity, gap between policy and practice, weak institutions, deployment of poor technological equipment and corruption have been attributed to some of the challenges in Nigeria's international borders, especially in developing countries.

Porous international borders have been found to hurt the achievement of sustainable development, such as loss of revenue, destruction of lives and infrastructure, small and light weapons proliferation, drug trafficking, child and human trafficking and general unrest created and fostered by foreign terrorist fighters (FTFs) and other criminal elements who come in through unmanned borders. This buttresses Blum's (2014) view that international borders are both melting pots and security hot spots necessary for development. Iregbenu and Uzonwanne (2015) pointed out that the challenges of transnational borders are obstacles to achieving sustainable development goals.

The Nigerian government, through customs, immigration services, and other security agencies, has attempted to address the challenges in its international borders. However, the problems persist. According to Bach (2005), primarily, border regions with a high rate of irregular migration create an atmosphere that is both chaotic and cluttered, overpowering the capacity of border enforcement agents. This is the situation of Nigeria's international borders today. Terrorism and banditry in the north have led to a surge in humanitarian aid of over 8.7 million people (Ojo, Oyewole & Aina, 2023).

The United Nations Children's Fund (2022) report asserts that Nigeria has the highest number of out-of-school children, about 10.5 million, the highest in the world; the attack on farms and farmers has stifled the government's effort at food self-sufficiency. Ladan and Matawalli (2020) aver that killing and kidnapping of farmers, chasing farmers out of their farmlands, seizure of farmlands, burning and raiding of grain silos, and blocking of local trade route areas negatively impacted food security. Thus, it has become pertinent to address security challenges emerging from Nigeria's international borders and examine their impact on sustainable development, for without peace and security, a nation cannot experience any meaningful development.

Border porosity is a global challenge, with every nation devising strategic ways and mechanism to manage, thus, international borders are a consequence and not a root cause militating against sustainable development. The capacity and investment on border management strategies by nations reflect on their border permeability and porosity. Therefore, to what extent has border challenges in these areas affected the prevalence of poverty and poor quality education? Are the border challenges in these areas a consequence of its long stretch? Are the incidences of corruption by security personnel a consequence of the border challenges?

The concept of Poverty and Quality Education

Poverty is a multifaceted concept; it is an absence of the basic needs of life, like clothing, food and shelter (Okalow, 2023). Gardeazaba (2020) defines poverty as the absence of sufficient material possessions or income to meet a person's needs. Roser (2021) aver that one of the sole determinants of a person's income is where they live and that people are not poor because of who they are but because of where they are. This aligns with Nelson Mandela's position that

poverty is artificial and can be subdued and eliminated by human feats (Morduch, 2008). According to the World Bank, 'Poverty is hunger. Poverty is a lack of shelter. Poverty is being sick and not being able to see a doctor. Poverty is not having access to school and not knowing how to read. Poverty is not having a job, fear for the future and living one day at a time (Economic and Social Inclusion Corporation (2009). The UN *International Poverty Line* is set at less than \$1.90 per day, that is, ₦950 (World Bank, 2022).

Similarly, Thinley as cited in Manoj (2022) opine that quality education is a multidimensional concept as what encompasses quality education depends on the objective set out. However, quality education from the United Nation's benchmark rest on a favourable environment, suitable curriculum and didactics, the physical condition of the learners, and an auspicious outcome (UNICEF,2000). Thus, quality education is dependent on peace and security, well informed teachers, healthy children and a safe learning environment. However, these elements are limited in the study area particularly in communities proximate to international borders. The frequent attacks and kidnapping in schools from the Chibok Girls (2014), Dapchi Girls (2018), and Kankara Boys (2020) amongst others, have further heightened tensions in these areas (Ojelu, 2021). According, to the Ummah Support Initiative (2023) the fraught security environment in northern Nigeria discourages teachers and parents leading to a decrease in school enrollment and attendance, thereby affecting education in the region.

International Border Challenges on Poverty and Quality Education

According, to the assessments of the United Nations Security Council Resolution 2178, terrorist and criminal activities at the international borders, have increased vulnerability of affected populations, supplied funds to terrorist and criminal networks and weaken the state's effort at securing their borders in a way that negatively affect global peace and security. These events undermine sustainable development by taking advantage of weak border systems, porous and unrestrained borders, and members of terrorist and transnational organised crime groups, as well as "Foreign Terrorist Fighters" (FTFs), consistently exploit the weakness of border security or their advantage (UNSCR, 2014). No Nigerian border can be declared impenetrable (Punch Editorial Board, 2023).

Achumba and Ighomereho (2013), Ujah and Eboh (2006) and Igbuzor (2011) substantially identify insecurity as one of the obstacles to sustainable development. They opinioned that development is unsustainable when an enlargement of human choice excludes, disconnects, promotes inequity, reflects imprudence or raises insecurity. Everest-Phillips (2014) points out that sustainable development demands that people are open to situations that weaken their capacity to meet their needs. While the concept of sustainable development applies to all nations, its peculiarity, priorities, and challenges differ from one nation to another.

Ladan and Matawalli (2020) observed that banditry characterised by killings, kidnappings, threats, robberies, theft, burnings, raiding and blocking of local trade routes has increased poverty in the border towns of Katsina. The impact has been severe because most of the deaths were among farmers or cattle herders and traders whose death meant their families and dependents became challenged by food shortages and, more often than not, had to move to internally displaced persons camps to survive. For example, on Sunday, 5th January 2020, the bandits blocked a section of Jibia to Batsari road to kidnap 38 traders returning from Jibia's weekly market. They interrupted crop harvesting and fishing in Jibia (Ibrahim, 2020).

Kangyang and Aipe (2021) noted that insecurity from the border areas could deter both students and teachers and may impede the student's academic performance. In December 2020, over 300 students were kidnapped by suspected gunmen from the Government Boys Science Secondary School in Kankara, Katsina State, few months later, bandits kidnapped 317 female students at Government Girls Secondary School Jangebe, Zamfara State. Peterside (2021) asserts that abduction represents a failure of the nation to protect its leaders of tomorrow and that school kidnappings in the north are a double-edged sword as they combine Boko Haram's regressive dogma that 'Western education is evil' and the ransom-seeking criminal profit motive. Kofi Annan succinctly captures this situation by the assertion that poverty anywhere is a threat to human security everywhere (United Nations, 2002).

Inadequate Infrastructure and Nigeria's International Border

Olomu, Alao and Eyitayo (2015) aver that Nigeria's borders are challenged with the need for more personnel, patrol vehicles, surveillance helicopters and equipment, as well as neglect or non-functioning of intelligence services. Musa (2013) opines that Nigeria must adopt innovative technologies such as radars, alarm systems, primary detector sensors for long remote surveillance platforms and sound intelligence services to secure her borders. He added that modern border equipment like the Blighter Radar, which can effectively survey both the land and low air zone concurrently, would be ideal for distant surveillance and detection of people and vehicles trying to cross the borders illegally, particularly in thickly forested terrains like the Ruggu forest that cut across Katsina and Zamfara border towns.

Achumba et al. (2013) assert that insecurity in border areas can be attributed to inadequate equipment and personnel in weaponry and training. Suliema (2021) observed that the bandits and criminals possess more sophisticated weapons than those of the security officials at the border due to a well-organised syndicate flourishing arms trade across Mali, Mauritania, Niger and Chad, which connects to the Zamfara state border.

The long stretch of Nigeria's international borders and Border challenges

Nigeria's border with its neighbouring countries spans 4745sq.km. Nigeria shares international borders with Cameroon (1,690 kilometres) in the east, Niger Republic (1,497 kilometres) in the north, Chad (87 kilometres) in the north-east and Benin Republic (773 kilometres) in the west (Babatola, 2015). Mustapha (2004) argues that most of these border areas are either mountainous or in the jungle, making effective surveillance of the borders difficult, with links to Mali, Libya, and Sudan difficult. Hazen and Horner (2007) linked the violence and insecurity in Nigeria's international borders to the lengthy and porous nature of Nigerian borders. This explains why Musa (2013) maintains that the vastness of Nigeria's international borders calls for a new strategy on the management and security of the borders, or else the fight against insurgency, banditry, arms trafficking and proliferation will remain a mirage.

Osimen, et al., (2017) discovered that Nigeria's trans-national borders have hundreds of illegal routes that connect to neighbouring African countries; from prudent evaluation by locals, there are over 250 footpaths from Damaturu/Maiduguri axis that leads directly to Cameroon, Chad and Niger. These paths are primarily unknown by security agencies, are unmonitored and unprotected and thus serve as leaky routes for arms and ammunition trafficking to Nigeria. Similarly, this is true at Illela, Kaita, Jibia and Maigatari borders. Furthermore,

Mailabari and Khan and Hamidu (2015) observed that the complex terrain of Nigeria's borders makes effective manning difficult, coupled with the government neglecting border communities regarding basic amenities, which accounts for the high illegal movement across borders. The frequent attacks on Katsina and Zamfara are sustained by inadequate security presence at Nigeria's borders with neighbouring countries, particularly Niger (Suliema, 2021). According to the World Trade Organisation (2022), membership countries of the World Customs Organisation (WCO) who have been exploring the latest advances in border technology management like Block chain, Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) and Internet of Things (IoT) maintain that it brought about immense benefits in areas like, improvement in transparency, information sharing with relevant agencies or stakeholders, lower labour cost and improved time of activities.

Corruption by Security Forces

According to Bala Usman, corruption is deliberate violations of standards of conduct for gainful ends, legally, professionally, or ethically, established in private and public affairs (Usman, 2001). In the Corruption Perceptions Index 2021, on a scale of 0-100, Nigeria's public sector stood at 76 points, with Nigeria ranking 154 out of 180 countries globally. The level of corruption among border management agencies and institutions is intense. Illegal arms supply to bandits in Northern Nigeria are conveyed from Maradi, the second largest city in Niger, through dozens of routes into states sharing borders with Niger, Zamfara, Katsina and Sokoto. Suleiman (2021) observed that checks were not carried out, but the drivers were asked to 'drop something', and this extortion is often done in collaboration with local miscreants.

Also, some security personnel are influenced by ethnic, religious, or communal sentiment and are easily influenced by their interest in serving their people rather than the nation. Thus, instead of being national watchdogs defending national interest and values and protecting people from harm by criminals, they soon become saboteurs of government effort by supporting and fueling insecurity through either leaking vital security information or aiding and abetting criminals to acquire weapons or escape the long arm of the law (Ladan, 2019b). According to Oludiran (2021), the Comptroller-General of the Nigeria Immigration Service (NIS), Muhammed Babandede, had admitted in a public broadcast in 2021 about reports of extortion from immigration officials in Katsina and had cautioned officers of the agency that there would be severe sanctions for such actions which are capable of bringing the country down.

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on Ole Weaver's theory of securitisation and Hans Morgenthau's theory of political realism.

Securitization Theory of International Border

Ole Waever and Barry Buzan advanced the securitisation theory in 1993, belonging to the Copenhagen school. The theory explains the necessity for state actors to reconstruct subjects from regular political issues into matters of "security", thereby permitting the exceptional measure to be used in the name of security. The constructivist school of international relations championed this theory, challenging core neo-realist and neo-liberal theoretical views (Buzan, Waever & Jaap de Wilde, 1998). Barry Buzan and Ole Waever assert that securitization theory

helps frame and shift an issue or concern from everyday politics into security. They outlined four principles of Securitization theory:

1. A securitising actor: an entity that makes the securitising move or statement;
2. An existential threat: an object (or ideal) that has been identified as potentially harmful;
3. A referent object: an object (or ideal) that is being threatened and needs to be protected;
4. An audience: the target of the securitisation act that needs to be persuaded to accept the issue as a security threat.

Buzan and Hansen (2009) explain that the acts of securitisation redefine an issue and its status by raising it from the standard level to the threat and security sphere, from the non-political and political, thereby elevating an issue from the policy level to the 'existentially threatening' stage (Buzan & Hansen, 2009, p. 214). Securitisation theorists argue that a subject that has been successfully securitised will receive greater attention and resources than subjects that have not been securitised, even when these other subjects cause more harm.

Abulof (2014) affirmed that the ability to securitise a given subject, like an international border, effectively depends on the status of a given actor, like the government and whether similar issues are generally perceived as security threats. Some countries have been able to rely on this theory by prioritising their international borders and categorising it as a matter of national security rather than a mere political affair. For instance, the United States of America has applied securitisation theory to address the America-Mexico border crisis. Likewise, the Russia-Ukraine international border crisis has become a significant security issue in international relations.

One of the weaknesses of the securitisation theory is that it appears to be 'problematically narrow' and strengthens the negative idea of security being turned into a commodity, undermining the various socio-political backgrounds (McDonald, 2008, Gad & Peterson, 2011).

This theory is appropriate for the study because international border challenges are not only issues of socio-economic and political concerns but majorly hinged on security issues. In other words, the existential threat, that is, porosity and the arbitrary nature of the borders, inadequate equipment and personnel, corruption, and undocumented migration, is a consequence of the securitising actor (Nigerian government and agencies) neglect to prioritise international borders as a security issue in Nigeria. This situation has significantly undermined sustainable development (poverty and education), thereby increasing the vulnerability of the Nigerian people.

Methodology

The study adopted the survey research design method to examine the challenges of international borders on sustainable development, primary sources of data collection was utilised. Three border communities were purposively selected based on the level of insecurity linked to border activities. The Taro Yamane formula was adopted to determine the sample size of the study.

The data was analysed using descriptive statistics.

Table 1: Population size of Kankara, Jibia, and Zurmi Local Government Area (LGA)

Local Government Area	Population
Kankara	434,700
Jibia	299,200
Zurmi	523,000
Total	1,256,900

Sources: National Bureau of Statistics (2022), (3.7% population projection)

Table 2

Local Govt Area	Population	Sample size	% of Sample size
Kankara	434,700	136	34
Jibia	299,200	96	24
Zurmi	523,000	168	42
Total	1,256,900	400	100

Table 2 above shows the population, number, and percentage of sample size of three (3) Local Government Areas under Study

Data Presentation/Analysis

Table 3: Questionnaire Distribution

Class	No distributed	Responses	Percentage response
Security officials (Customs/Immigration/Police border patrol)	120	105	54%
Family Heads	95	90	46%
Total	215	195	100%

Out of 215 questionnaires distributed, 195 found useable. One hundred five to security officials and 90 to family heads, 54% and 46% responses were returned, respectively.

Table 4: Responses to Questionnaire- Security Officials

Do you consider that you are well equipped to meet the influx of illegal immigrants?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	15	14%
No	90	86%
Total	105	100%

While 14% of Security Officers responded that the government provide adequate equipment, 86% said they are inadequate.

Table 5: Responses to Questionnaire

Do you have adequate asylums at borders for illegal immigrant?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	0	0%
No	105	100%
Total	105	100%

Adequate Asylums at Borders

100% of the Security Officers indicated that there are no asylums for illegal immigrants at Nigeria’s international borders.

Table 6: Responses to Questionnaire

Can you cope with the long stretch of route you are manning? If not, why?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	5	5%
No	100	95%
Total	105	100%

Can Security Officers Cope with Long Stretches?

95% of the security officers responded that they needed help coping with the long stretch of the borders they were posted on.

6b. Reasons for not coping with the long stretch of borders

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Inadequate workforce	15	14%
Lack of digital surveillance equipment	5	5%
All of the above	85	81%

Reasons for Not Coping with Long Stretches of Borders

85% of the security officials attested to the inadequate manpower and digital surveillance equipment as reasons for not coping with the long stretch of border patrol.

Table 7: Responses to Questionnaire

Is there sufficient biometric equipment at the border to verify identification of persons?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	20	19%
No	85	81%
Total	105	100%

Biometric Equipment for ID Verification at Border

81% of security officials admitted that there is no sufficient biometric equipment at the borders.

Table 8: Responses to Questionnaire

Do you consider special border forces necessary for patrol?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	70	67%
No	35	33%
Total	105	100%

Necessity of Special Border Forces for Patrol

67% of the Security officials responded that Special Forces are necessary for border patrol to stop the influx of illegal immigrants, and 33% responded that it is not necessary.

Section B- Family Heads

Table 9: Responses to Questionnaire-Family Heads

Has your family income decreased due to the activities of terrorists and bandits?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	90	100%

No	0	0%
Total	90	100%

Family Income Decrease Due to Terrorism/Banditry

Ninety families, representing 100%, responded that family income had decreased due to border insecurities.

Table 10: Responses to Questionnaire

Have any of your children been displaced from school due to the activities of terrorist and bandits?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	75	83%
No	15	17%
Total	90	100%

Children Displaced from School Due to Terrorism/Banditry

83% of the respondents agreed that at least one child in the family has been displaced from school due to the activities of terrorist and bandits, while 17% have not been affected.

Table 11: Responses to Questionnaire

Have you lost any family members due to the activities of terrorists and bandits?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
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Yes	60	67%
No	30	33%
Total	90	100%

Family Members Lost Due to Terrorism/Banditry

67% of the respondents admitted that they had lost at least one family member as a result of terrorist activities emanating from Nigeria's international borders. In comparison, 33% claimed that they had not lost any family members.

Table 12: Responses to Questionnaire

Have school terms been interrupted due to terrorist and bandit activities?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	85	94%
No	5	6%
Total	90	100%

School Terms Interrupted Due to Terrorism/Banditry

94% of the families responded that the activities of terrorist and bandits have interrupted the school calendar, while 6% responded that it has not.

Table 13: Responses to Questionnaire - Farmers/others

As a farmer, are you able to access your farm freely with the activities of terrorists and bandits?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	65	72%
No	25	28%
Total	90	100%

Farmer Access to Farms Due to Terrorism/Banditry

72% of the farmers responded that the activities of terrorist and bandits have affected their farming, while 28% responded that they are not involved in farming.

Table 14: Responses to Questionnaire

Do you spend less than ₦900 per day for food and upkeep?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	72	80%
No	18	20%
Total	90	100%

Spending less than ₦900 per day for Food and Upkeep

80% of the families responded that their daily expenditure per person is less than ₦900 per day, while 20% of the families responded that their daily expenditure per person is more than ₦900 per day.

Table 15: Responses to Questionnaire

Have you observed security officials collecting money from persons and motorists crossing the border?

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	88	98%
No	2	2%
Total	90	100%

Observed Security Officials Collecting Money

98% of the families responded that security officials collect money from motorists and persons crossing the border, while 2% responded that they have not witnessed this.

Data Analysis

The study was analysed using descriptive statistics

The study sought to establish if international border challenges impact sustainable development, focusing on poverty and education. The questionnaire sought to find answers

to the attributes that may likely affect poverty and education; 94% of respondents who were security officials agreed that the provision of equipment to do their jobs is grossly inadequate. In addition, 100% of the security personnel polled agreed that there is no asylum at the border post. In response to the questionnaire, the security personnel also agreed that they need help to cope with adequately manning the long stretch of the borders; they attributed this to an inadequate workforce and lack of digital surveillance equipment as factors militating against effective border policing. They established the need for special border patrol forces to complement their efforts.

As expressed by the security personnel at the Nigeria border office and post, the challenges above have direct consequences on the people living in these border communities. 100% of the responses from the family head in these border communities agreed that their income had suffered severe depletion as a result of the activities of cross-border terrorists and bandits. 83% of family heads advanced that their children have severally been displaced from school as a result of the nefarious activities of these cross-border bandits and terrorists. Furthermore, 67% of these family heads agreed that they had lost at least one family member due to the activities of these terrorists. 72% of the family heads pointed out that the activities of terrorists and bandits have disrupted access to their farmlands, even as 80% of family heads confirm that their daily spending is less than ₦900 per day (which is less than the UN International Poverty Line of \$1.90 per day). Eighty-eight family heads, constituting 98%, agreed that they have seen security officials collecting money from persons and motorists crossing the international border post.

Findings

The interdependence between international borders and sustainable development, particularly poverty and education, is invaluable. Aristotle succinctly captures this when he asserts that extreme poverty is the parent of revolution and crime (Anon, 2020). This aligns with the majority of research findings that a high level of illiteracy, poverty, and unemployment are among the root causes of misconduct, banditry, and terrorism in the study areas.

The findings further, reveal that inadequate technological equipment and a lack of digital surveillance systems and border management gadgets, which could have supported border security efforts and covered the shortage of personnel, need to be improved. Also, the inadequate manning of the long border stretch has to a large extent, led to the near collapse of Nigeria's international border security and enhanced the border porosity between Niger and Chad. This finding resonates with that of Philip and Osimen (2022), Ladan (2019) and Willie and Okunade (2021).

Other scholars (Brunet-Jailly & Dupeyron, 2007) contend that it is natural for borders to be porous. Thus, it is the prerogative of lawmakers in charge of security strategy to identify that the porosity of borders is influenced by the relative degree and system engaged by human interaction through the borders. Therefore, when there is an upsurge of human activities across an international border or border communities, whether for cultural, economic, or political reasons, the government response must be decisive, either in collaborating or redesigning a new strategy. This aligns with the perspective of Holdich (1916) that good

international borders are those that balanced economic pressures or reduced political hitches between countries.

Furthermore, this study found out that porosity is a consequence of not attending to international borders as a security issue. Neo-Realist and neo-Liberals see the challenges of international borders as a weakness on the part of the State to increase its power, promote peace, reduce poverty and increase economic well-being. Securitisation theory views it as the inability of the State to raise international borders not only to a high level of importance but to a much higher level than is given to politics, economy, religion and culture (McGlinchey et al.,2017).

Furthermore, the study established that there has been a decrease in family income due to poor access to farmlands and loss of lives because of the activities of criminal element at the border communities. The combination of these factors has accentuated the level of poverty in these border communities. Also, the pervasiveness of border porosity has led to an influx of terrorists and bandits, leading to frequent kidnappings, which has resulted in the interruption of the school calendar. The result of this is a drastic fall in the level of school enrollment among children of school age in these border communities. These findings validate the study of Kangyyang and Aipe (2021) and Peterside (2021) that insecurity is connected to the low level of literacy and poverty.

Likewise, the study affirms that corruption among border security officials stems from socio-cultural, religious affinity, and poor welfare, which accounts for the high level of compromise among border security officials. This corroborates Suliema's (2021) and Ladan's (2019b) findings that some security personnel have become saboteurs of government efforts.

Conclusion/Recommendations

This study examined the challenges of international borders on sustainable development in some border communities in Katsina and Zamfara states. It establishes a relationship between international border challenges and sustainable development; the poor management of border security due to inadequate equipment, unmanned borders, shortages of personnel and lack of digital surveillance has intensified the porosity of Nigeria's international borders. The study was able to establish that the activities of miscreants that are thrown up by the activities at these border communities have led to poverty and a drop in school enrollment, exacerbating the already low level of illiteracy in the region.

International borders should provide safety and control for a nation by being a wall of deterrence against criminal elements. The study therefore recommends that the Nigerian government through its ministry of Internal Affairs (Immigration) and ministry of Finance (Customs) should invest in the latest Border Surveillance System (BSS) and technologies like the Blighter Radar and train personnel on biometric technologies both for the surveillance of regular and irregular migrants. Furthermore, the Nigerian Customs Service should take advantage of being a member of the World Customs Organisation (WCO) to benefit from ongoing transformation in the Internet of Things (IoT), block chain, and distributed ledger technologies (DLT) to ensure adequate border security.

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